

PARACHOR OF CHROMIUM TRIOXIDE IN WATER

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The experimental value of parachor of CrO_3 supports the view that ionic parachors are smaller than atomic parachors and CrO_3 ionises in water by forming either chromic or dichromic acid.

In our previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 225, 492) we have shown that the parachors as determined by solution method will give correct value only if ionic and atomic parachors of elements are the same. The actual experimental work shows that they should be different. The works of Lakhani and Daroga (*ibid.*, 1938, 18, 37, 320) and of Ray (*ibid.*, 1938, 18, 43) support our view. We have extended this work to chromium trioxide in aqueous solutions. The constitution of chromium trioxide on the basis of electronic theory of valency

is represented as $\text{O}=\overset{\text{O}}{\underset{\text{O}}{\text{Cr}}}$ or there is one double bond and two semipolar bonds. Hence the

parachor of $\text{CrO}_3 = P_{\text{Cr}} + 3P_{\text{O}} + P_{\text{double bond}} + 2P_{\text{semipolar bond}} = 54 + 60 + 23 \cdot 2 - 3 \cdot 2 = 134$.

The actual value obtained by us is in the neighbourhood of 103. This low value clearly indicates that CrO_3 exists in solution in ionic form by combining with water and forming H_2CrO_4 or $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. The lower value obtained by experiment is in agreement with the view that ionic parachors are smaller than atomic parachors for the same element. Similar considerations with $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ support the fact that CrO_3 ionises in solution. Results are given in the tables below :

where γ = Surface tension of the solution. P_m = Parachor of the mixture. P_s = Parachor of the solute. X = molar fraction of the solute. d = Density of the mixture.

Parachor of Chromium Trioxide

The results of parachor of chromium trioxide at different concentrations in aqueous solution ($P_{\text{water}} = 52 \cdot 6$) are recorded below :

TABLE I

Temp.	Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_3)} = 0 \cdot 15139$			$x_{(\text{CrO}_3)} = 0 \cdot 13263$			
		γ	P_m	P_s	Density.	γ	P_m	P_s
20°	1·488	72·01	59·61	102·4	1·424	71·34	58·72	102·7
30	1·484	71·71	59·89	104·1	1·415	71·03	59·05	105·1
40	1·478	71·44	60·26	106·2	1·408	70·50	59·13	105·8
50	1·470	70·84	60·40	107·6	1·402	69·58	59·32	107·2

TABLE II

Temp.	Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_3)} = 0 \cdot 10028$			$x_{(\text{CrO}_3)} = 0 \cdot 11727$			
		γ	P_m	P_s	Density.	γ	P_m	P_s
20°	1·361	69·98	57·28	100·3	1·380	70·52	57·98	103·0
30	1·353	69·36	57·51	102·4	1·373	70·33	58·26	105·4
40	1·346	69·04	57·76	104·6	1·366	70·11	58·41	107·2
50	1·337	68·68	58·05	107·3	1·359	69·81	58·59	107·9

TABLE III

Temp.	Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.095103$			Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.02940$			P_{H_2}
		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .	
20°	1.320	70.74	56.67	104.6	1.111	72.34	53.30	103.4	
30	1.313	70.25	56.89	104.8	1.105	70.81	53.14	105.7	
40	1.309	69.60	56.96	105.0	1.101	69.72	53.18	105.9	
50	1.302	69.08	57.15	106.1					

TABLE IV

Temp.	Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.05666$			Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.1538$			P_{H_2} .
		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .	
21°	1.200	71.61	54.89	101.4	1.491	73.81	60.19	104.6	
30	1.196	71.06	54.94	102.3	1.483	73.40	60.43	106.2	
40	1.190	69.44	54.93	102.3	1.474	72.88	60.68	107.8	
50	1.185	68.45	54.95	102.5	1.465	72.16	60.91	109.2	

TABLE V

Temp.	Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.08078$			Density.	$x_{(\text{CrO}_2)} = 0.06904$			P_{H_2} .
		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .		γ .	P_{m} .	P_{H_2} .	
20°	1.277	71.42	56.20	101.5	1.243	71.76	55.44	100.5	
30	1.270	70.87	56.13	102.0	1.237	70.78	55.48	101.1	
40	1.262	70.05	56.42	105.1	1.229	68.96	55.46	100.8	
50	1.260	68.17	56.15	102.1	1.224	67.76	55.46	100.6	

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